

0.4 KV OVERHEAD NETWORKS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS

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ANNOTATION

Subjects of relations in the field of energy saving and energy efficiency improvement are the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, administrative-territorial units of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, legal entities, individuals, including individual entrepreneurs, foreign countries, foreign and international legal entities (non-legal entities).

SIP-2 3x95 + 1x95 self-retaining insulated wire (type 2) with aluminum and steel-aluminum conductors up to 3x95 mm² + 1x95 mm², coated with a light-stabilized cross. -bonded polyethylene insulation.

Nominal alternating current voltage is 1 kV

The number of cores is 3 + 1 additional core

The cross-sectional size is 95+95 mm²

1 km CIP-2 3ch95+1x95 weighs 1480 kg

The mass of aluminum in 1 meter of wire is 1.03 kg.

The weight of wire in all drums depends on the specification of a particular manufacturing plant. To calculate the weight of the SIP-2 3x95+1x95 cable with a drum, it is enough to know the weight of one meter of wire. *SIP-2 3x95+1x95 sim diametri*

Outer diameter of SIP-2 wire 3x95 + 1x95: 44 mm

The outer diameter of the conductor depends on the specifications of a particular factory

The size of the wire is taken into account when calculating and choosing the right current-carrying systems.

Nominal alternating voltage	1 kV
Nominal frequency	50 Hz
Main fibers	Multi-fiber
Electrical resistance of 1 km of conductor	0.32 Om/km
Active resistance of a current-carrying wire at 90 ° C at a frequency of 50 Hz	0.411 Om/km
Neutral wire	
Electrical resistance of 1 km of conductor	0.363 Om/km
Active resistance of a current-carrying wire at 90 ° C at a frequency of 50 Hz	0.466 Om/km

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Continuous load current

For a load factor of 100% when operating in normal operation mode

Asosiy tolalari	300 A
Nuytral sim	300 A

The value of the current flowing through a fixed wire is calculated at an ambient temperature of 25 ° C, a wind speed of 6 m / s and an intensity of solar radiation of 1000 W / m.

Short-circuit current of SIP-2 3x95+1x95

The value of the short-circuit current flowing in 1 second in SIP-2 3x95+1x95 is 8.8 kA (kiloamperes).

The minimum permissible bending radius during laying - (diametric 10mm wire)	440 mm
Construction length	300 m
Code OKP SIP-2	3553320900
Expiry date	At least 40 years
The warranty period for working with the cable	3 yil
Ambient temperature during cable operation	от -60 °C до 50 °C
Minimum low-temperature performance of the cable before heating	-20 °C
Active resistance of a current-carrying wire at 90 ° C at a frequency of 50 Hz	0.466 Om/km

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Permissible heating temperature of cable conductors:

A long time	90 °C
in overload mode	130 °C
Short circuit limit is	250 °C

Designation of SIP-2 3x95 + 1x95 with abbreviations.

C- self-restraint

I - izolirovanny- Isolated

P - conductor - conducting wire

Type 2 design

3- the number of main phase wires

95- cross-sectional area of main conductors, mm²

1-neutral wire

95- cross-sectional area of the neutral conductor wire, mm²

Color designation is made in the form of long colored lines with a width of at least 1 mm. As a rule, red, green, blue, yellow and white colors are used.

Marking by embossing or printing with numbers and letters should be done with an interval of not more than 500 mm. The height of numbers (letters) should be at least 5 mm, width - at least 2 mm (minimum width for number 1 is 1 mm).

List of used literature

1. Abdumutallib o'g'li, E. A. (2022). Reliability of Collector (Bottle) Set in ACS. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8, 251-255.
2. EA Abdumutallib o'g'li Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 3 (5), 1897-1901

3. EA Abdumutallib o'g'li Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies 8, 251-255